

Oxidation of Methyl Group : Kinetics of Cerium(IV) Oxidation of 2-Methyl Benzthiazole, Benzoxazole and Benzimidazole in Acetic-Perchloric Acid Mixture

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Ceric ion oxidation of 2-methyl benzthiazole, benzoxazole and benzimidazole has been examined at $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.5M - 2.0M$ following the disappearance of cerium titrimetrically. The rates are consistent with a mechanism involving the rapid formation of a complex which disproportionates to form the products. The rate increases with increase of $[\text{HClO}_4]$ and ionic strength indicating a positive salt effect. Evidence for complex formation is obtained from Michaelis Menten reciprocal plots. The activation parameters are compared.

THE kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of organic compounds by Ce(IV) have received considerable attention during the past few years^{1,2}. Although a large number of organic compounds have been studied, the kinetics of oxidation of methyl groups in the heterocyclic compounds have not been studied extensively so far. In a short communication on the oxidation of *alpha* picoline by Ce(IV)³, we reported that the oxidation proceeded through a free radical mechanism and the product of oxidation was found to be an aldehyde. In this paper we report the results on the kinetics of oxidation of 2-methyl benzthiazole, benzoxazole and benzimidazole by Ce(IV) in acetic-perchloric acid medium in order to investigate the effect of hetero atoms on the kinetics.

Experimental

2-Methyl benzthiazole and 2-methyl benzoxazole (Riedel) were triple vacuum distilled before use. 2-Methyl benzimidazole was recrystallised from 50% alcohol-water. All other chemicals were of BDH (AnalaR) quality. A stock solution of Ce(IV) was prepared by dissolving ceric ammonium nitrate in 4.0 M perchloric acid and standardised against ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin as indicator. 30% aqueous solution of acetic acid was used as the medium for the reactions, since above compounds are insoluble in aqueous phase.

The rate measurements and the calculation of the rate constants were made according to our previous conditions³.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The reaction mixtures containing excess of Ce(IV) were left over

night in a thermostated bath and the unreacted Ce(IV) in the reaction mixtures was determined in the usual method. It was found that 4 moles of Ce(IV) are required for each mole of the substrate oxidised and the stoichiometry may be presented as follows :

R represents benzthiazole (BT), benzoxazole (BO) and benzimidazole (BI).

The reaction products were identified as follows :

Aliquot (2 ml) of the reaction mixture was pipetted into 50 ml of 2 N hydrochloric acid saturated at 0° with 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine. Additional 10 ml of hydrochloric acid was added to ensure the solubility of hydrazine. After 30 to 60 min at 0° the 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazones of the corresponding aldehydes were collected.

The products were isolated and characterised by the usual methods. The products of the oxidation were found to be the corresponding 2-aldehydes confirmed by monitoring the reaction mixture in glc and comparing the retention time with the authentic samples. Further, the formation of the products, i.e., the corresponding aldehydes were confirmed by the ir spectra.

Results and Discussion

The reactions were found to be first order with respect to Ce(IV) in the range 0.0075-0.075 M as

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evidenced by the linearity of the plots of $\log [(Ce(IV))] vs$ time upto 75% of the reaction. However, it was noticed that at constant $[Ce(IV)]$ the order with respect to the substrates is not simple and the slopes of the plots of $\log k vs \log [sub]$ are not strictly unity.

Further, at constant ionic strength, the plots of $1/k_{obs}$ against $1/[Substrate]$ (Fig. 1) were linear making reasonable intercepts on $1/k_{obs}$ axis, thus satisfying Michaelis-Menten reciprocal relationship*. Hence, initial complex formation is indicated in all the cases.

Fig. 1. Michaelis-Menten plot. $[Ce(IV)] = 12.5 \times 10^{-3} M$; HOAC=30% (v/v).
 (●) Benzimidazole 40°; $[HClO_4] = 1.25 M$; $\mu = 1.5 M$
 (▲) Benzthiazole 40°; $[HClO_4] = 1.35 M$; $\mu = 1.5 M$;
 (■) Benzoxazole 30°; $[HClO_4] = 0.5 M$; $\mu = 0.75 M$.

The effect of bisulphate ion on the rate was investigated in perchloric acid solutions. There would be a slight tendency of bisulphate and H^+ to associate forming H_2SO_4 . Bisulphate ions retarded the rates considerably, indicating that the bisulphate complexes of $Ce(IV)$ are less reactive species for the oxidation. The rate of the reaction increased with increasing ionic strength, indicating a positive salt effect. Moreover, the rate of oxidation increased with $[HClO_4]$.

The effect of varying solvent composition on the rate of oxidation has been studied. The rate of the reaction increased with increase in proportion of acetic acid in the reaction mixture. This dependence of rate on the solvent composition may be explained by the approaches of Ingold⁶, Laidler and Eyring⁶ and Amis⁷. The reaction can be classified as an ion dipole reaction, the positive species being the ionic oxidant. It is also seen that plots of $\log k vs 1/D$ give linear relationship showing that one of the reactants is an ionic one. Positive slopes of the lines give indication of charge, since

according to Amis, in an ion dipole reaction involving positive ionic reactant, the rate would decrease with increase of dielectric constant of the medium.

Mechanism of the reaction : Careful examination of the results indicates that the oxidation of 2-methyl heterocyclic compounds proceeds through a free radical intermediate. Evidence for the free radical intermediate is provided by the induced polymerization of acrylonitrile.

Depending on the concentration of perchloric acid, ceric ion may be present in this medium¹⁰ as $Ce(H_2O)_9^{3+}$ and $Ce(OH)(H_2O)_8^{2+}$. Monomeric, dimeric and trimeric aceto-ceric(IV) complexes were also detected spectrophotometrically⁹ in acetic acid-perchloric acid systems. Since the predominant species is monomeric in perchloric acid range 0.2-2.0 M⁹, the equilibrium can be written as follows :

The rate of oxidation increases with increasing $[H^+]$ and so the unhydrolysed species (II) would be the active one. The species (II) can react with the substrate to form the complex III. This in a slow step, generates free radical which in subsequent stages of reaction with $Ce(IV)$, is converted to the aldehyde. The reaction scheme can be represented as in eqns. (3)-(8).

The rate expression from equations (3)-(8) is (9), from which equation (10) follows, where k_{obs} is the observed rate constant.

$$\frac{-d[Ce(IV)]}{dt} = k_{obs} [Ce(IV)]$$

$$= \frac{K_1 K_2 k_2 [Ce(IV)] [R-CH_2] [H^+]}{K_1 K_2 [H^+] [R-CH_2] + K_1 [H^+] + 1} \quad \dots (9)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{k_2} + \frac{1}{[R-CH_2]} \left[\frac{1 + K_1 [H^+]}{K_1 K_2 k_2 [H^+]} \right] \quad \dots (10)$$

Accordingly at constant $[H^+]$, plots of $1/k_{obs}$ against $1/[substrate]$ should be linear and it is observed to be so (Fig. 1). The values of k_s are found to be 8.3×10^{-4} , 2.0×10^{-4} and 1.6×10^{-4} sec^{-1} in case of 2-methyl benzoxazole, 2-methyl benzthiazole and 2-methyl benzimidazole respectively.

The results for the oxidation of different methyl substituted compounds in the temperature range $35-50^\circ$ are given in Table 1. Comparing the thermodynamic parameters as evidenced from Table 2, the

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE RATE
[Ce(IV)]=0.0125 M; [Substrate]=0.0125 M; HOAC=30% (v/v)

Temp. °C	$k_{obs}(sec^{-1}) \times 10^4$
2-Methyl benzoxazole ($[HClO_4]=0.5 M; \mu=0.75 M$)	
30	17.0
35	24.4
40	46.0
45	81.0
2-Methyl benzthiazole ($[HClO_4]=1.35 M, \mu=1.5 M$)	
35	4.0
40	5.6
45	12.3
50	21.8
2-Methyl benzimidazole ($[HClO_4]=1.25 M, \mu=1.5 M$)	
40	4.1
45	8.5
50	16.3

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR
Ce(IV) OXIDATIONS

	E K cal/mole	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ Cal/deg/mole
2-Methyl benzoxazole	19.8	-12.4
2-Methyl benzthiazole	22.5	-8.07
2-Methyl benzimidazole	28.5	+8.3

order of the reactivities may be presented as follows :

The sequence of reaction can be explained if the mechanism of the reaction as suggested in equations

(3) to (8) is assumed. The 2-methyl substrates combine with the active species of Ce(IV) forming a complex in a fast step. The rate limiting step is, therefore, the decomposition of the complex forming the corresponding free radical at the methyl carbon atom. So the reactivities of different 2-methyl compounds will depend on the stability of the free radical at the methyl carbon atom. In the reaction condition studied by us, the hetero atoms will very likely combine with the protons forming the corresponding protonated ions. The stability of the free radical will, therefore, depend on the nature of the protonated hetero atoms.

In case of benzimidazole, since ammonium ion is very stable, the free radical will not derive much stability from the electrons of the nitrogen atom. The reactivity of 2-methyl benzimidazole will, therefore, be expected to be the least of all.

Sulphonium ion is more stable than oxonium ion. Arguing as above, the free radical on the methyl carbon will be stabilised more in 2-methyl benzoxazole than in 2-methyl benzthiazole. The observations, therefore, correspond to the expected sequence of reactivity.

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